

Development of New Side Impactor

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SUMMARY

In this study, as a door side impact beam, new side impactor was developed by inserting circular composite tubes into square composite tube. As a result, new side impactor showed higher energy absorption capability than that of square tube without circular tube when the quasi-static lateral compression tests were performed.

Keywords: Side impact beam, Occupant protection, lateral collision, energy absorption, GFRP, Pultrusion tube

INTRODUCTION

In lateral collision, the ratio of a fatal accident is very high. Therefore, the protection of an occupant from side impact is important. However, a door of car must have thin thickness to make occupant's cabin wide. That is to say, the side impactor needs to have higher energy absorption capability.

Traditionally, metals can absorb impact energy by deforming plastically and therefore have been used for crashworthy structural applications in automobiles. On the other hand, there is a considerable amount of published data on the energy absorption characteristics of polymer composite materials. It is well established that the polymer composite materials with proper design achieve higher specific energy absorption than the conventional metals^[1,2]. The fracture mode is called progressive crushing, which proceeds under constant load. This unique potential of polymer composite materials has generated considerable interest in recent years for crashworthy structural applications in aircraft and automotive vehicles.

In this study, new side impactor for the energy absorption material in side impact, which can be used as reinforcement of a door module, was suggested. A schematic drawing and photograph of the new side impactor are shown in Figure 1 (a) and (b). The impactor with square section has many circular tubes in the inside. The circular tube is also energy absorption materials. That is to say, synergy effect for the energy absorption capability can be expected by combination of these tubes. The quasi-static lateral compression test of the new impactor was performed and the energy absorption capability was investigated.

Figure 1 New side impactor

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The side impactor was made from two kinds of pultrusion tube (Fukui-fibertech Co.,Ltd). In the pultrusion tube, glass fiber reinforced plastic was used. Matrix resin was epoxy resin. The size of square pultrusion tube was 50 x 50 and the thickness was 4mm. The size of circular pultrusion tube was ϕ 30 and the thickness was 3mm. At first, 45 degrees taper was made at one end of the circular tube. Afterward, the circular tube was cooled quickly by liquid nitrogen to be able to insert the circular tube into the square tube easily. And the inserting of circular tube in the inside of square tube was performed by pressing.

In experimental method, the quasi-static axial compression test of only circular pultrusion tube was executed by using INSTRON testing machine at a constant cross-head speed of 5mm/min. to investigate the energy absorption capability. Next, the quasi-static lateral compression tests of new side impactor were performed by using INSTRON testing machine at a constant cross-head speed of 5mm/min. The compression test in the square tube without circular tube was also performed to compare with new side impactor. After test, the appearance of new side impactor was observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Energy Absorption Capability of Circular Tube

Figure 2 shows load-displacement curve of circular tube in compression test. The load increased rapidly in initial stage and then showed peak in the displacement of 2.5mm. After displacement of 5mm, the crushing load showed a constant value. The average load under progressive crushing was 17.5kN. Table 1 shows specific energy absorption value (E_s value) of circular tube. As an object of comparison, E_s value of steel tube was listed. Here, E_s value is well used for evaluating energy absorption performance of materials. E_s value of circular pultrusion tube was 1.3 times higher than that of steel tube. Figure 3 (a) and (b) show photograph of fractured tube. Crush zone spread out towards both sides of the tube.

Figure 2 Load-displacement curve in compression test

Table 1 Specific energy absorption value (E_s value) of circular tube

	E_s value [kJ/kg]
Circular tube	42.3
Steel	33.6

(a) Side view

(b) Upper view

Figure 3 Photograph of fractured circular tube

Lateral Compression Behaviour of New Side Impactor

Load-displacement curves in quasi-static lateral compression test are shown in Figure 4. And photographs on compression test are shown in Figure 5 (a) and (b). The loads of the square tube without circular tubes decreased immediately in the load value of 40kN. It was seen that the square tube was broken on the corner part from the result of photographs. However, new side impactor kept a high load after the increase of initial load. And the load gradually decreased. From the photographs on compression test, even if the square tube was broken, it was considered that the circular tubes were broken

by generating the progressive crushing. According to this result, new side impactor could absorb high crushing energy.

Figure 4 Load-displacement curves in quasi-static lateral compression test

(a) New side impactor

(b) Square tube without circular tube

Figure 5 Photographs on quasi-static lateral compression test

Photograph after quasi-static lateral compression test in the circular tube existed inside of square tube is shown in Figure 6. Two kinds of crushing modes were

confirmed in the tube at both ends. In the A area, the crush zone spread out towards inside and outside of the tube. However, the crush zone was bended toward inside of the tube in the B area. Especially in the central tube, all crush zones were bended toward inside due to the lack of spreading area. Therefore, it was considered that fracture mode was not perfect progressive crushing. That is to say, it is expected that if the crushing mode shows perfect progressive crushing, the energy absorption capability of new side impact would be improved more.

Figure 6 Photograph of side impactor after quasi-static lateral compression test

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the development of a side impactor was noticed because lateral collision caused a fatal accident well. As a door side impact beam, a quasi-static lateral compression tests were performed by using two types of square pultrusion composite tubes; a square tube with circular pultrusion tubes inside and without circular tube. As a result, square tube with circular tube inside (New side impactor) showed higher energy absorption capability than that of square tube without circular tube. However, the circular tube existed inside of square tube did not show the perfect progressive crushing. It is expected that if the crushing mode shows perfect progressive crushing, the energy absorption capability of new side impact would be improved more.

References

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